

Contemplations about axion generation in gyrotrons, magnetrons and other crossed field devices and related detection options for a low cost experiment

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There are many proposals and running experiments for the detection of axions in the microwave range since many years. Here I would like to share my contemplations about certain ideas which were not yet really discussed very widely yet.

The concept I like to present, is to use the “well known” method already applied in CROWS to bring the effective resolution bandwidth (RBW) down to the range of a few microHz via phase-locked generators and receivers. This works surprisingly well [1,2] and had been developed for LSW (light shining through the wall) experiments in the microwave range. In this case the absolute frequency uncertainty and phase noise of a (high power) microwave source does not matter as long as the receiver is in close tracking. Of course we do not assume really free running sources but some sort of power amplification device which is driven by a modern synthesizer that has already an absolute stability well beyond the ppm range.

The basic idea is to use a very powerful cross field device (CFD) like a (relativistic) gyrotron or magnetron (available CW power levels in the Mega-watt range) and to assume that due to the presence of a strong DC magnetic field and some powerful RF field and strongly accelerated electrons, possibly axions are created. The receiver would be a shoebox sized box with a classical TM_{010} type receiver cavity say above 20 GHz and some 1 to 2 tesla permanent magnet and some low noise preamplifiers followed by an optical fiber link to a VSA (vector spectrum analyzer) “somewhere”. This VSA is in phase lock via the 10 MHz reference from the generator or some common 10 MHz reference, driving the high power microwave device.

The point is, to construct (box in the box in the box concept) a really leak-tight room temperature microwave receiver (shielding >300 dB) with power supply via battery or through an optical fiber link (good enough for a few Watt). Output signal transmission of course also via optical fiber and analog modulation. This had already been demonstrated experimentally and with success by CROWS [3] about 10 years ago. The high power microwave device may operate into some dummy load or for some other application thus the proposed experiment could be done entirely “parasitic” with little investment in time, money and manpower and a “dynamic range” (better amplitude margin) of about 300 dB (possibly more). The shoebox size “leak-tight” receiver could then be placed in a suitable position as close as possible to the Gyrotron, magnetron etc but still avoiding to stay there in some fringe magnetic field and not exposed to any significant X-rays (maybe additional X-ray shielding required) possibly generated from such high power devices.

One important parameter is to select the right frequency..of course this would first be depend on the hardware available (e.g. a 30 GHz gyrotron). But there is a vague and faint hint to go to near 42 GHz from an entirely unexpected direction. In the early 80s there were experiments by Keilmann, Grundler et al. (MPI Stuttgart/Germany) [4] on low level microwave irradiation

related changes in the growth rate of yeast cultures in that very frequency range. But that experiment (trying to provide evidence for subthermal biological effects of microwaves) could not be successfully replicated later and elsewhere and thus became sort of forgotten. However and this may sound really far fetched (maybe crazy)..perhaps the effect on the yeast culture did not come from microwaves but rather from axions generated by the (low power) magnetron or other crossed field device used there at that time (strong magnetic field, accelerated electrons and moderate RF power) .

Obviously presenting this idea as axion experiment to some reviewers in order to get funding is unlikely to receive very strong support since the result is of course uncertain .But one could sell it much more easily as challenging EMI/EMC experiment to demonstrate 300 db level difference between the gyrotron power and the very well shielded external axion converter.A gyrotron or some other CDF running full power is likely to have leakage levels outside “in the hall” in the ballpark of milliWatt/cm². But if all this is defined a EMI/EMI experiment as master of PhD work a nice results is predictable (and thus fundable) with respect to EMI/EMC and with a lot of good luck also axions or paraphotons are found. As for the “amplitude margin”(not dynamic range) the numbers are 1 MW=+90 dBm versus -220 dBm for 10 micro-Hz resolution bandwidth (i.e. one weekend data taking) at room temperature and a noise figure of 3 dB thus in total 310 dB.

Refs:

[1] F. Caspers, S. Federmann, D. Seebacher ; CERN-BE-Note-2009-026 ;CERN-TE-Note-2009-001; [Demonstration of 1E⁻²² Watt Signal Detection Methods in the Microwave Range at Ambient Temperature](#), Geneva July 2009

[2] M. Betz, F. Caspers; [A microwave paraphoton and axion detection experiment with 300 dB electromagnetic shielding at 3 GHz](#), IPAC '12 (new Orleans) May 2012

[3] [Betz, M](#) (CERN) ; [Caspers, F](#) (CERN) ; [Gasior, M](#) (CERN) ; [Thumm, M](#) (Karlsruhe U.) ; [Rieger, S W](#) (Karlsruhe U.) ; First results of the CERN Resonant Weakly Interacting sub-eV Particle Search (CROWS); [Phys. Rev. D 88 \(2013\) 075014](#) ;Oct 2013

[4] W. Grundler and F. Keilmann; Sharp Resonances in Yeast Growth Prove Nonthermal Sensitivity to Microwaves; [Phys. Rev. Lett. 51, 1214](#) – Published 26 September 1983